

DOI: <https://10.5281/zenodo.17981186>

EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to investigating the mechanisms of endothelial dysfunction in arterial hypertension based on scientific literature and international research findings. Studying the role of endothelial dysfunction in arterial hypertension is considered one of the important issues, as early correction of this condition can significantly reduce the risk of developing future cardiovascular diseases. The article provides a detailed explanation of normal endothelial function, endothelial dysfunction and the physiological processes involved in maintaining these mechanisms, as they manifest in arterial hypertension.

Keywords: Hypertension, endothelial dysfunction, aerobic exercise, oxidative stress.

INTRODUCTION

The endothelium is not just a passive barrier between blood and tissues. It is an active organ and its dysfunction is an essential factor in the development of almost all cardiovascular diseases, atherosclerosis, arterial hypertension, ischemic heart disease and chronic heart failure. Endothelial dysfunction is also involved in inflammatory reactions, autoimmune disorders, diabetes mellitus, thrombosis, sepsis and tumor growth. The mechanisms by which the endothelium contributes to the beginning and progression of these conditions are varied. They include not only the control of vascular tone but also participation in atherogenesis, thrombus formation, inflammatory processes and maintenance of vascular wall integrity. Three main groups of stimuli that activate endothelial cells can be identified: 1. **Hemodynamic changes**, especially increased shear stress. 2. **Platelet-derived mediators** such as serotonin, adenosine

diphosphate, and thrombin. 3. **Circulating local neurohormones** including catecholamines, vasopressin, acetylcholine, endothelin, bradykinin, and histamine. These mediators and neurohormones act mainly through specific receptors on the surface of endothelial cells. Some substances can also influence endothelial cells through non-receptor mechanisms, directly crossing the cell membrane [1].

Nitric oxide

The term endothelial dysfunction is used to describe the altered metabolism of available nitric oxide (NO) or imbalance of several endothelium-derived relaxing and constrictor factors. Between the blood and the vascular wall, the endothelium forms both mechanical and biological barrier. Interactions between platelets and leukocytes with the vessel wall, impairment of vascular tone, inflammation, free radical formation and oxidation of lipids and vascular smooth muscle cell proliferation can be activate endothelial cells (ECs). ECs function by secreting relaxing and/or contracting molecules. ECs are exposed to the shear stress resulting from blood flow and can convert mechanical stimuli into intracellular or biochemical signals (e.g., proliferation, apoptosis, migration, permeability, remodeling and gene expression). As a result, endothelial dysfunction is related to several diseases including atherosclerosis, cancer metastasis, inflammatory diseases and hypertension. Hypertension is defined as the presence of chronically elevated systemic arterial or diastolic blood pressure (BP) above a certain threshold whereas sustained hypertension is defined as systolic BP >140 mm Hg in medical environment and daytime ambulatory systolic BP >135 mm Hg, and/or medical environment diastolic BP >90 mm Hg and daytime ambulatory diastolic BP >85 mm Hg. Thus, the patients with sustained hypertension have increased BP levels in the medical environment (in clinics or office) and out of the medical environment (at home). Sustained high blood pressure is also an indicator of the age, diet, stress, sedentary lifestyle, all or the combination of these factors. It has been suggested that sustained hypertension is closely related to both target organ damage and organ function failure including heart, kidneys and brain. Pathophysiology of hypertension is related to several factors, including genetics, activation of the sympathetic nervous system, the rennin-angiotensin (AT)-aldosterone system, endothelial dysfunction, impaired capillary blood flow and inflammatory mediators [2].

Chart 1. **Schematic presentation of endothelial dysfunction leading to Hypertension. IMT-intima media thickness;NO-nitric oxide; PWV-pulse wave velocity;RAAS-renin angiotensin-aldosterone axis;ROS-reactive oxygen species;VOL-blood volume.**

Oxidative stress

Oxidative stress has been implicated in the patho physiology of many cardiovascular conditions, including hypertension. ROS significantly increase the influence of stimulants such as inflammation, radiation, high partial oxygen pressure, advanced age, obesity and chemical substances. Oxidative stress that increases on a cellular level results in oxidative damage by altering the structure of molecules such as deoxyribo nucleic acid, amino acid, protein, lipid and carbohydrate. A particularly important radical for cardiovascular biology is superoxide, which is formed by the one-electron reduction of oxygen. Superoxide can serve as both an oxidant and as a reductant and is a progenitor for other ROS. Other radicals include the hydroxyl radical, lipid peroxy radical and alkoxy radicals. Other molecules, including peroxynitrite, hypochlorous acid and hydrogen peroxide are not radicals but have strong oxidant properties and are, therefore, included as ROS. Another a group of molecules is the reactive nitrogen species (RNS) including NO, the nitrogen dioxide radical, and the nitro sodium cation. The main sources for oxidative excess in the vasculature are adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase (NOX), xanthine oxidase, the mitochondrial and uncoupled NOS [3].

Recent studies have sought to further characterize the mechanisms behind hypertension induced oxidative stress and inflammation. Multiple sources of oxidative stress have been implicated in the pathogenesis of hypertension-related endothelial dysfunction [4]. Investigations over the past year have gone further to investigate the

potential mechanisms regulating two important sources of hypertension-associated oxidative stress: nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase and mitochondria [5,6]. Isolated carotid arteries from mice were exposed to increasing intraluminal pressure and showed concomitant reductions in endothelium-dependent vasodilation to acetylcholine, increases in vascular superoxide production, and increased NADPH oxidase activity [7].

Impact of Aerobic Training

Regular moderate physical activity (PA) — such as walking, jogging, cycling, or swimming — reduces systolic blood pressure by 6–10 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure by 4–8 mmHg in patients with hypertension. Regular physical exercise also contributes to **body weight reduction** and **improves the lipid profile**, primarily by increasing high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol levels and reducing triglyceride levels. Furthermore, it **reduces platelet aggregation** and **enhances fibrinolytic activity**. Recent epidemiological studies have shown that **aerobic exercise** reduces the incidence of cardiovascular complications and overall mortality in the general population. A meta-analysis of 48 randomized trials on physical activity (PA) lasting up to 6 months, including 8,940 patients with stable ischemic heart disease, reported a **20% reduction in all-cause mortality** and a **26% reduction in cardiovascular mortality** among patients engaging in PA. Moreover, regular PA contributes to the **reduction of endothelial dysfunction** and **systemic inflammation**, which are known to play a critical role in the development and progression of atherosclerosis [8].

I. Physical exercise serves as a **non-pharmacological intervention** that enhances cardiorespiratory fitness, reduces inflammation, aids in managing cardiovascular risk factors, optimizes muscle quantity and quality, and improves endothelial function.

II. The most effective exercise modality for increasing circulating **endothelial progenitor cells (EPCs)** in healthy populations remains unknown.

III. Long-duration aerobic exercise has been found to have more profound effects on endothelial progenitor cell levels compared to maximal and submaximal exercise.

IV. There is a direct relationship between training frequency and improvements in endothelial function among healthy individuals.

V. Physical activity has been associated with enhanced endothelial function in middle aged and elderly subjects, mitigating the adverse effects of aging on arterial wall properties.

VI. Studies examining the chronic effects of various forms of exercise on circulating endothelial progenitor cell numbers in healthy adults have yielded conflicting results, possibly due to factors such as age, exercise prescription, and cardiovascular risk factors.

VII. While cross-sectional studies comparing physically active and inactive individuals and longitudinal exercise training studies in healthy populations show minimal effects on endothelial function, improvements are consistently observed in subjects with abnormal baseline endothelial function, including the elderly and patients with heart failure or coronary artery disease.

VIII. The beneficial effects of physical activity and exercise training on vascular endothelium suggest another **cardioprotective effect** of habitual exercise on vascular aging and atherosclerosis progression.

IX. Aerobic-based cardiac rehabilitation serves as a non-pharmacological treatment for enhancing endothelial function in heart failure patients, with higher training frequency and intensity yielding a greater adaptation of endothelial function.

X. The optimal “dose” of exercise for improving endothelial function remains unclear, necessitating further research to evaluate the role of exercise intensity and type in positively impacting the endothelium [9].

CONCLUSION

Endothelial dysfunction plays a key role in the patho-genesis and progression of HTN and its complications. Early identification and management of ED is the most potential approach in the successful management of not only HTN but also ASCVD in early stages which will strongly impact not only the patient’s morbidity and mortality but in general will also have a large impact on the cost and disease burden on the society. Research oriented to recognize factors producing ED and development of drugs particularly addressing endothelial function will definitely improve prognosis in HTN and prevent HMOD. OCP use has been associated with ED and increased incidence of ASCVD. Further understanding of the mechanism of OCP-induced ED will definitely make use of OCPs safe in coming days.

ED — *Endothelial Dysfunction*

HTN — *Hypertension*

ASCVD — *Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease*

HMOD — *Hypertension-Mediated Organ Damage*

OCP — *Oral Contraceptive Pills*

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